

From 0 (dB) to 15 (dB) in 13 (years):

Extended developmental trends in the spatial release of masking for highly informational maskers

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1) Motivation: To better understand Auditory Processing Disorder (APD) in children ...

- through investigation of a specific proposed type of APD known as *Spatial Processing Disorder* (SPD) said to affect ~20% of children with APD
- Not a general SPD, but an impairment in the Spatial Release of Masking (SRM), the improved performance listeners obtain when maskers are spatially separated from a target voice.

4) Using two spatial conditions only

- See graphic above at right (SRM changes little with increases in separation > 45°, as used here)

5) Participants

- Typically-developing children with normal hearing & no evidence of neurological/developmental disorders
 - aged 5.1 – 18.2 years
 - 29 in primary school & 46 in secondary = 75 in total

6) Results (at right)

- Clear difference in developmental trends, with SRTs improving by ...
 - ~2 dB in the collocated condition (**Sp0**)
 - ~17 dB in the separated condition (**SpSep45**)
- Concerning SRM ...
 - ~15 dB change over the age range
 - SRM > 0 only when age > ~7.5 years
- Note that the SRM in the LiSN-S is substantial even at age 6, but changes by far less into adulthood (~3 dB over the age range of our study)

7) Why the difference in SRM trends?

- CCRM has ...
 - All 3 talkers starting at the same time
 - Masker speech containing possible responses
- LiSN-S has ...
 - Multiple cues to detect the onset of the target talker (warning beep plus appearance of the new speech)
 - Masker speech that is typically unrelated to the target sentences
- So CCRM has fewer cues to aid auditory scene analysis and directing attention to the relevant talker

2) SPD has only been diagnosed through a particular test, the LiSN-S

- Listening in Spatialized Noise-Sentences Test [2] ...
 - estimates SRTs (dB) – Speech Reception Thresholds
 - (the SNR necessary to perform at 50% correct)
 - Listener repeats simple sentences from a female talker
 - With two female masking talkers reading unrelated connected passages continuously
- Four conditions (but only 2 matter here) vary spatial aspects and whether the masking talkers are the same or different from the target (see graphic at left)
 - Symmetric placement of masking talkers eliminates a consistent 'better ear listening' so taps binaural skills

3) Our aim: To implement a task tapping similar skills that would be linguistically simpler and not require a spoken response

- Using the *Children's Coordinate Response Measure* (CCRM), based on the prior CRM (graphic far left).
 - 6 animals, 6 colours & 8 digits – all monosyllabic
 - three young male talkers
 - 'dog' always identifies the target talker
 - target talker chosen randomly on each trial, with each of the other two talkers serving as masking talkers

8) Conclusions

- Using the CCRM to diagnose (so-called) SPD in younger children cannot work!
- Younger children get no SRM in this task with a high degree of informational masking, which may reflect their inability to ignore distractor speech even when the talkers are spatially separated

References

- [1] Cameron, S., Glyde, H., & Dillon, H. (2012). Efficacy of the LiSN & Learn auditory training software: randomized blinded controlled study. *Audiol Res*, 2(1), e15. <https://doi.org/10.4081/audiore.2012.e15>
- [2] Cameron, S., & Dillon, H. (2007). Development of the Listening in Spatialized Noise-Sentences test (LiSN-S). *Ear and Hearing*, 28(2), 196-211.

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